

Synthesis, Spectral Behaviour and Antimicrobial Activity of some Mono-, Di- and Tri-cationic Pyrazolocyanine Dyes

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New cationic penta- and octa-methine cyanine dyes incorporating pyrazolo nucleus were prepared. The new cyanines were identified by elemental, ir and nmr spectral data. Spectral behaviour in uv-vis absorption spectra of the cyanines have been discussed. Bactericidal and fungicidal activities of the selected cyanines were tested.

CYANINE dyes have various applications, such as photosensitisers in photographic processes¹. They possess various bactericidal activities².

In this paper, new cationic pyrazolomethine cyanines (**2a-c**, **3a-c**, **5a-c**, **6a-c** and **10**) were prepared to study their spectral behaviour for photosensitisation effect and their biological activity against bacteria and fungi.

Results and Discussion

Interaction of equimolar amounts of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-oxopyrazolo-4-yl-methylidene-2-(quinolinium-1-ethiodide)cyanine (**1**)³ with aromatic aldehydes in the presence of piperidine afforded the corresponding monocationic pyrazolopentamethine cyanine (**2a-c**, Scheme 1). Such cyanines, brownish violet to intense violet in colour, exhibited green fluorescence in organic solvents. They are soluble in concentrated H₂SO₄ and the solutions liberated iodine on warming. Their ethanolic solution gave yellow colour in acidic medium which turned violet on basification with alkali hydroxide.

The structures of compounds **2a-c** were established by the elemental and ir spectral data (Tables 1 and 2). Quaternisation of **2a-c** with ethyl iodide gave the corresponding dicationic pyrazolopentamethine cyanine (**3a-c**). The colour of **3a-c** ranged from violet to intense violet, and they were soluble in organic solvents giving green fluorescence. The structures of **3a-c** were confirmed by elemental and ir spectral data (Tables 1 and 2).

Selective oxidation⁴ of **1** with SeO₂ in ethanol gave the corresponding 3-formyl derivative (**4**), whose ir spectral data are summarised in Table 2. The direct interaction of **4** with 2(4)-methylpyridinium- or quinolinium-2-yl salts under piperidine

Scheme 1

catalysis gave the corresponding dicationic pyrazolopentamethine cyanines (**5a-c**). **5a-c**, brown to violet in colour, exhibited red to green fluorescence in organic solvents. They are soluble in concentrated H₂SO₄ and the solution liberated iodine on warming. Their ethanolic solutions gave yellow colour in acidic medium which turned red or violet on basification. The structures of **5a-c** were confirmed from elemental, ir and nmr spectral (Tables 1 and 2) data. Interaction of equimolar amounts of **1** and **4** in the presence of piperidine

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2, 3, 5 AND 6*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Formula	Colour of product	Absorption spectra	
						λ_{\max}	ϵ_{\max}
2a	H	148	50.60	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ OI	Brownish violet	390 530	(4 300) (4 700)
2b	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	146	80.00	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ I	Reddish violet	380 540	(1 400) (1 200)
2c	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	132	46.80	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ I	Shiny violet	380 520	(1 350) (1 550)
3a	H	180	45.50	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ OI ₂	Brownish violet	380 535	(1 250) (8 800)
3b	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	140	47.33	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ I ₂	Reddish violet	380 545	(2 500) (8 750)
3c	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	155	47.36	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ I ₂	Shiny violet	380 540	(1 500) (7 800)
5a		132	54.00	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ OI ₂	Violet	360 350	(12 200) (10 600)
5b		175	71.30	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₄ OI ₂	Intense violet	350 550	(3 000) (6 000)
5c		184	31.20	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ OI ₂	Brown	360 536	(9 400) (5 700)
6a		145	44.00	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ I ₂	Brown	485 585	(21 000) (21 500)
6b		126	65.80	C ₄ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂ I ₂	Shiny brown	488 547	(18 500) (24 250)
6c		140	33.70	C ₄ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂ I ₂	Reddish brown	885 590	(14 750) (17 500)

*Analyses for C, H and N found satisfactory.

the corresponding dicationic pyrazolo-octamethine cyanines (6a–c). 6a–c possess some characteristic colours in their solid state or in solutions in most organic solvents. Their structures were established by elemental and ir spectral data (Tables 1 and 2).

Tricationic bispyrazolo-octamethine cyanine (10) was obtained by the following two routes: (i) quaternisation of 6b was carried out with ethyl iodide to give 10, and (ii) the tetraoxobispyrazolo compound (9) was reacted with bimolar amounts of 1-ethyl-2-methylquinolinium-2-yl salts under piperidine catalysis to give 10 which were identical (m.p. and m.m.p.) with those prepared by route (i).

The structures of 9 and 10 were confirmed from elemental, ir and nmr spectral data (Table 2).

Spectral behaviour: The uv-vis absorption spectra of the monocationic pentamethine cyanine (2a–c) in 95% ethanol consist of single and broad band, whose position and molar extinction coefficient are influenced by the type of aryl substituents (Table 1). The quaternisation of these compounds at the pyrazolo nucleus intensifies the absorption bands with slight red-shift. This red-shift is more pronounced in case of electron-deactivating group (Table 1). On the other hand, substituting the aryl moiety in 2a–c by a quaternary heterocyclic nucleus causes a remarkable red-shift with strong intensification of the absorption band relative to the monocationic pyrazolocyanine dyes (2a–c) or the dicationic derivatives (3a–c).

The absorption spectra of 5a–c show bathochromic shift in absorption band with those containing quinolinium-2-yl salt and hypsochromic shift with those containing pyridinium-2-yl or 4-yl salts (5a, c). The spectra of dicationic bispyrazolo-

TABLE 2—IR AND ¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF SELECTED COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)*	δ (CDCl ₃)*
2b	1 620–1 600 (C=O), 1 750–1 720 (C=O), 1 590–1 550 (C=N), 2 990–2 940 (ethiodide of heterocyclic residue)	7.4 (15H, m, Ar, heter.), 4.5 (2H, d, OH=OH), 6.5 (1H, s, =OH), 3.9 (2H, q, CH ₂), 1.3 (3H, t, CH ₃), 2.0 (2H, s, <i>p</i> -OCH ₃)
3b	2 990–2 940 (ethiodide of heterocyclic residue), 1 620–1 600 (C=O), 1 730–1 700 (C=O), 1 580–1 530 (C=N)	8.1 (15H, m, Ar, heter.), 4.3 (2H, d, OH=CH), 6.5 (1H, s, OH), 3.95 (4H, q, 2 CH ₂), 1.3 (6H, t, 2 CH ₃), 2.0 (3H, s, <i>p</i> -OCH ₃)
4	1 740 (CHO), 1 700–1 695 (C=O), 1 620–1 600 (C=O), 2 990–2 940 (ethiodide of heterocyclic residue)	7.5 (11H, m, Ar, heter.), 6.5 (1H, s, =OH), 6.8 (1H, s, CHO), 3.3 (2H, q, CH ₂), 1.3 (3H, t, CH ₃), 2.0 (3H, s, OCH ₃)
5b	1 610 (C=O), 1 500 (C=N), 3 000–2 950 (ethiodide of heterocyclic residue)	8.1, 7.4 (m Ar, heter.), 1.6 (3H, t, CH ₃), 2.3, 2.5 (1H, s, OH=N), 3.4 (2H, d, OHC=O), 3.8 (2H, q, CH ₂)
6b	1 660–1 620 (C=C conj.)	—
9	1 710 (C=O), 1 500 (C=N), 1 600–1 580 (C=O), 2 990–2 900 (ethiodide of heterocyclic salt)	7.5 (10H, m, Ar), 4.3 (2H, d, CH=OH), 3.7 (2H, q, CH ₂), 1.3 (3H, t, CH ₃)
10	1 600–1 580 (conj C=O), 1 710–1 700 (C=O), 1 570–1 540 (C=O), 2 990–2 900 (N-quaternary heterocyclic salt)	8.1, 7.4 (m, Ar, heter.), 1.9 (3H, t, CH ₃), 2.0 (2H, s, 2 =OH), 2.2, 2.3 (2H, d, CH=OH), 3.4 (2H, s, 2 CH conj. with C=O)

*F. Scheinman, "An Introduction to Spectroscopic Methods for Identification of Organic Compounds", 1970, Vol. 1, p. 41.

octamethine cyanine dyes (6a-c) show two bands in the visible region at 385-488 and 530-547 nm. The shorter wavelength is strongly red-shifted relative to the dicationic pyrazolopentamethine cyanines (5a-c). A comparison of the absorption spectra of the symmetrical dicationic bispyrazolopentamethine cyanine (6b) with those of asymmetrical analogues (6a, c) shows that the symmetry at the cyanine molecule causes a red-shift by 12-17 nm with intensification of the absorption band (Table 1).

The quaternisation of 6b to give the corresponding tricationic compound (10), causes separation of the absorption bands with decrease in their molar extinction coefficient. This behaviour is due to the extra quaternary center at one of the pyrazolo nuclei which acts as an additional electron-sink in the electronic transition pathway.

Biological activity: The antimicrobial activity of some of the compounds (2a-c, 3a, 5a, b and 10) was tested against bacteria (*B. stearotherophilus* 92 and 98, *Serratia* and *Sarsina* sp.) and fungi (*Aspergillus terreus*, *Penicillium notatum* and *Alternaria*).

Structure-activity relationship was demonstrated relative to the monocationic pyrazolopentamethine cyanine (2a-c). Thus, 2a-c is biological active with aryl substituent (X=H and *p*-NO₂) against both bacteria and fungi, but inactive having *p*-OCH₃ moiety. Dicationic pyrazolopentamethine cyanines incorporating phenyl or pyridinium-2-yl salt moieties (3a, 5a) are more potent against both bacteria and fungi relative to their analogues (3b, c; X=*p*-OCH₃, *p*-NO₂; or 5b; A=1-ethylquinolinium-2-yl salt) (Table 3). Finally, it was obvious that the dicationic and or tricationic bispyrazolo-octamethine cyanines (6a, b, 10) are less biological active towards bacteria and fungi.

Experimental

The ir spectra (KBr) were determined on a Pye-Unicam SP 1100 spectrophotometer, and electronic spectra on a Unicam SP 8000 spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched silica cells. Melting points are uncorrected.

3-Methyl-1-phenyl-5-oxopyrazolo-4-yl-methylidene-2-(quinolinium-1-ethiodide) cyanine (1), 3-formyl-4,5-dioxo-1-phenylpyrazoline (7) and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-4,5-dioxopyrazolinium-2-yl salt (8) were prepared as reported earlier^{3,4}.

Monocationic pyrazolopentamethine cyanines (2a-c): Equimolar amounts of 1 (0.01 mol) and the aromatic aldehydes (benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde or *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde) were refluxed in ethanol (20 ml) containing piperidine (1 ml) for 10-12 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered while hot, evaporated to half its volume, cooled and acidified with acetic acid, followed by addition of water to yield 2a-c. The solid products were filtered, washed several times with water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol (2:1) (Table 1).

Dicationic pyrazolopentamethine cyanines (3a-c): 2a-c (0.5 g) was suspended in excess of ethyl iodide (5 ml) and heated at 170° for 5 h in a sealed tube and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with ether and crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

3-Formyl-1-phenyl-5-oxopyrazolo-4-ylmethylidene-2-(quinolinium-1-ethiodide) (4): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and SeO₂ (0.01 mol) was refluxed in ethanol for 12 h. The red amorphous precipitate of Se was removed by filtration. The filtrate was concentrated (20 ml) to yield 4 as orange-brown crystals from ethanol, (82%), m.p. 135° (Found: N, 8.51. C₂₂H₁₈N₂O₄I calcd. for: N, 8.69%); λ_{max} 385, 543 nm (ε_{max} 8 600, 1 700 m⁻¹ cm²).

Dicationic pyrazolopentamethine cyanines (5a-c): A mixture of 4 (0.01 mol) and 2(4)-methyl quaternary salts 2(4)-methylpyridinium-(quinolinium)-2-yl salt (0.01 mol), absolute ethanol (20 ml) and piperidine (1 ml) was refluxed for 6-10 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and crystallised from aqueous ethanol (Table 1).

Dicationic bispyrazolo-octamethine cyanines (6a-c): Equimolar ratio of 1 and 4 (0.01 mol) were dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) containing piperidine (1 ml) and refluxed for 13 h. Separation of the products were carried out as described above (Table 1).

Synthesis of tetraoxobispyrazolo-2-yl salt (9): Equimolar amounts of 4,5-dioxo-3-formyl-1-phenylpyrazoline (7) and 4,5-dioxo-3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazolinium-2-yl salt (8; 0.01 mol) were dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) containing piperidine (1 ml) and refluxed for 17 h. The reaction mixture upon filtration, concentration and crystallisation from aqueous ethanol yielded brown crystals (9; 60%), m.p. 115° (Found: N, 10.70. C₂₂H₁₇N₄O₄I calcd. for: N, 10.60%).

Tricationic bispyrazolo-octamethine cyanine (10): **Route (1):** 6b (0.5 g) was suspended in excess ethyl iodide (5 ml) and heated at 170° for 5 h in a sealed tube and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with ether and crystallised from ethanol, (51.77%), m.p. 165° (Found: N, 7.75. C₄₆H₄₁N₆O₂I₃ calcd. for: N, 7.70%); λ_{max} 370, 420sh and 555, 605 nm (ε_{max} 15 500, 10 000, 16 250 and 16 250 m⁻¹ cm²). **Route (2):** A mixture of 9 (0.01 mol) and bimolar ratio of 1-ethyl-2-methylquinolinium-2-yl salt (0.02 mol), ethanol (20 ml) and piperidine (1 ml) was refluxed for 18 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered hot, concentrated, acidified with acetic acid and diluted with water, and the resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol to yield 10 which had the same m.p. and m.m.p. (165°) as obtained from route (1).

Biological screening: Some selected cyanines (2a-c, 3a, 5a, 6a, b and 10) were screened using filter paper disc method⁵ and it was found that they

TABLE 3—BIOLOGICAL SCREENING DATA OF SELECTED COMPOUNDS

Compound tested Organism used	Inhibition zones (mm)*							
	2a	2b	2c	3a	5b	6a	6b	10
<i>B. steurotherophilus</i> (92)	9	—	8	11	—	—	—	—
<i>B. steurotherophilus</i> (98)	8	—	8	10	—	—	—	—
<i>S. sps.</i>	—	—	14	—	9	—	8	—
<i>S. sps.</i>	12	—	11	14	12	—	—	—
<i>A. terreus</i>	8	—	8	10	8	—	—	—
<i>P. notatum</i>	9	—	10	11	9	—	—	—
<i>Alternaria</i>	7	—	8	9	8	—	—	—

* (-) = Negative.

have remarkable activity against some bacterial and fungal strains (Table 3).

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